

Source: [Heravi, M.M.](#), Asadi, S., Sedghi, R. (2017), Pd Nanoparticles Immobilized on Supported Magnetic GO@PAMPS as an Auspicious Catalyst for Suzuki–Miyaura Coupling Reaction, *Journal of Catalysis Letters*, 147(8), [doi: 10.1007/s10562-017-2089-2](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10562-017-2089-2).

Pd Nanoparticles Immobilized on Supported Magnetic GO@PAMPS as an Auspicious Catalyst for Suzuki–Miyaura Coupling Reaction

[Majid M. Heravi](#)¹, Shima Asadi, Roya Sedghi

¹ Department of Chemistry, Faculty of Physics & Chemistry Alzahra University, Vanak, Tehran, Iran.

Abstract

A novel catalytic system based on palladium nanoparticles (Pd-NPs) immobilized onto the surface of graphene oxide (GO) modified by poly 2-acrylamido-2-methyl-1-propanesulfonic acid decorated with magnetic Fe₃O₄ was designed, prepared and fully characterized. It was successfully examined as a highly efficient heterogeneous catalyst in the Suzuki–Miyaura cross coupling reaction. The results showed excellent catalytic activity for the cross coupling of aryl bromides, alkyl iodides as well as aryl chlorides as the challenging substrates. It was easily separated by an external magnet and reused without any pre-activation at least in seven consecutive runs without any loss in its catalytic activity as well as any detectable Pd leaching. This study demonstrates the great potential of polymeric-functionalized GO as a support owing to its high loading and suitable dispersing of Pd-NPs, for the development of metal–graphene nanocomposites in industrial scale.

Keywords

Graphene oxide (GO), Heterogeneous catalyst, Magnetic nanoparticles, Palladium nanoparticles (Pd-NPs), Pd-catalyzed reaction, Suzuki–Miyaura reaction, Catalyst activity, Catalysts, Chemical reactions, Graphene, Magnetism, Nanomagnetism, Nanoparticles, Catalyzed reactions, Graphene oxides, Magnetic nano-particles, Palladium nanoparticles.